

The importance of learning english in high school education

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ABSTRACT *This article talks about the importance of learning English in high school, enthusiasm for language learning, and modern methods promoted by teachers to actively participate in classes.*

Key words: *Innovation, grammatical structure, secondary school, phonetic changes, primary education.*

Young children have a very high desire to learn a language, especially with current information and communication tools, this situation shows high indicators. On the part of our state, the conditions created in schools, the fact that the classrooms are equipped with modern technologies, the provision of young educated personnel, the organization of television online classes on online TV channels for all classes for independent study in addition to school classes are commendable. In the inductive method, grammar rules are first explained to students and then reinforced through examples. This method is often useful for high school students. For example, tenses, prepositions, articles are known terms for high school students. In the deductive method, the topic is first introduced through certain games and exercises, and then it is explained based on the rules. Since elementary school students do not have knowledge about possessives, participles, verbs and other units, it is more effective to explain the topic to them through games and songs. For example, Can is a modal

verb in English and is taught through handout materials. According to psychologists, compared to older people, children are 70-80% more interested in new things, reading and learning. Children try to perform tasks that they cannot perform even in our daily life despite warnings. They get bored of the sameness very quickly, therefore, it is necessary for the teaching staff to organize lessons in new ways, in an unconventional way, to fully create the environment of the foreign language being studied. Therefore, teachers should organize lessons using interactive, innovative and interesting methods. It is required to introduce students to work individually, in groups and in pairs, in the form of various competitions, in the form of games, to conduct lessons with the use of colorful visual aids, and to prepare separately for each lesson. This type of lessons increases love and passion for the language, activates inactive students, and creates healthy competition among students. Competition is the foundation of growth. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest. Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way: - through songs and poems to teach words and phrases that are difficult to explain or remember, without meaning. For

example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

- games related to mental and physical activities; - cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language. - role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: one student shows a dog howling, a cat meowing, another student can show which animal these sounds are.

- subject environment; If the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, the children will learn the language better. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) will give. This situation strengthens the students' vocabulary, language abilities, and expands their worldview. After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these thoughts,

the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies

in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them.

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